

TRENDS OF POLICY IN BANKS AFTER COVID-19 PANDEMIC IMPACTING ON ECONOMIC-FINANCIAL SYSTEM

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Abstract. Crises are good reminders of the key role that banks play in the economic system. The efficiency of the process through which savings are channelled into productive activities is crucial for growth and welfare. Lenders of funds are primarily households and firms. These lenders can supply funds to the ultimate borrowers – who are mainly firms, governments and households – in two ways. The first is through financial markets (money markets, bond markets, and equity markets). The second is through banks and other financial intermediaries. Thus, banks are a crucial part of the saving/lending process, especially in bank dominated financial systems such as Europe and Japan. It is therefore important to analyse their main functions and business models to understand how the challenges that these institutions are currently facing may affect the sustainability of the industry and the economy.

Keywords: banks, business model, Fintech, financial intermediation, investment, capital, financial indicators, cooperation, financial performance, profitability, financial risk.

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Covid-19 will accelerate some existing trends in the banking sector, will temporarily reverse others, and will influence the players in the sector (including the regulators). Covid-19 will deepen and lengthen the period of low or negative interest rates and will accelerate digitalisation and increase investment in IT, with operational risk and cyber-attacks on the rise. It will temporarily increase NPLs, hurting profitability, impairing the ability of banks to generate capital and buffers and constraining their capacity to provide loans. In the euro area, it will reinforce the doom loop between sovereign and bank risk, since the foreseen large increases in debt-to-GDP ratios, in particular in Southern Europe, may raise problems of sovereign debt sustainability over the medium term. The Covid-19 crisis will also lead to a temporary relaxation of capital and liquidity requirements. However, over the long run the outcome may be the opposite to protect against tail events, which seem to happen more often than expected. In the pre-Covid-19 world, banks were facing the challenges of low interest rates, the legacy of the global crisis with high NPLs, new competitors and digitalisation and a much heavier regulatory burden. In the post-Covid-19 world, these challenges will intensify, with only temporary alleviation of the regulatory burden due to the impending crisis.

The Covid-19 crisis makes evident that low interest rates are here to stay for much longer than was expected before the crisis. The prospect of negative economic growth and higher indebtedness will translate into even lower interest

rates, both nominal and real, with several central banks – including in the UK and US (see Table 1) – already having declared an extended LIRE period. This will lead to further pressure on banks’ profitability and, in turn, cutting of costs. Low rates will continue to reduce banks’ net interest margins, but may help contain default by firms and preserve collateral values somewhat, thus mitigating the new increase of NPLs. In any case, banks will again suffer a surge of NPLs due to the crisis which, together with persistent low profitability, will impair their ability to generate capital, constraining the capacity to provide loans to the real sector.

Banks remain exposed to credit risk in lending to the economy during the crisis, at least as regards loans outside of or beyond the coverage of government guarantees. Both central banks and regulators have taken measures to enable banks to keep lending during the crisis (see Table 1). Central banks have implemented a number of measures to ensure liquidity to banks and credit to the economy, such as the ECB’s modified TLTRO-III and the re-introduced LTRO policies, and relaxed criteria for collateral eligibility in liquidity operations. Regulators and supervisors have relaxed a number of regulations to reduce the potential procyclicality of measures introduced in the last two decades and to avoid a credit crunch.

Table 1. Main policy measures to enhance banking activity due to the Covid-19 pandemic, by jurisdiction.

Policy measure	United States	Euro area	United Kingdom
Regulatory relief	Reduced reserve requirement to zero Technical change to TLAC to help the use of buffers	Banks temporarily able to operate below the level of capital defined by P2G, CBB and on liquidity by LCR EBA postponed stress test exercise to 2021 Flexibility in prudential treatment of NPL and loan provisioning	Countercyclical capital buffer rate to 0% PRA cancelled the 2020 stress test Relaxation of some prudential measures
Liquidity support	Plan to purchase \$75 billion Treasury securities and \$50 billion GSE MBS PDCF lending to security firms and MMLF to assist MMFs in meeting demand for redemptions Provide up to \$2.3 trillion in loans, mainly through the PPP, MSLP and TALF	Additional LTROs and new PELTROs to safeguard money market conditions TLTRO III can be as low as 50 basis points below the average deposit facility rate PEPP to purchase public and private securities of €1.35 trillion until at least June 2021	Introduction of TFSME, financed by the issuance of central bank reserves CCFF will purchase commercial paper to provide support to firms with liquidity shortages

Interest rate policy	Plan to purchase \$75 billion Treasury securities and \$50 billion GSE MBS PDCF lending to security firms and MMLF to assist MMFs in meeting demand for redemptions Provide up to \$2.3 trillion in loans, mainly through the PPP, MSLP and TALF	Additional LTROs and new PELTROs to safeguard money market conditions TLTRO III can be as low as 50 basis points below the average deposit facility rate PEPP to purchase public and private securities of €1.35 trillion until at least June 2021	Introduction of TFSME, financed by the issuance of central bank reserves CCFE will purchase commercial paper to provide support to firms with liquidity shortages
Interest rate polic	Cut fed rate to a range of 0-0.25% Reduced rate discount window to 0.25%	No changes in the reference rates	Reduced bank rate to 0.1%
Collateral policy	New repo facility, FIMA, to smooth functioning of financial markets	Expanded range of eligible assets under the CSPP to non-financial commercial paper Temporary package of collateral easing measure	Activated CTRF to alleviate frictions in money market

Supervisors have provided temporary relief by allowing banks to fully use their capital and liquidity buffers, and have relaxed accounting procedures, introducing more flexibility in the criteria for loan classification as well as in the implementation of IFRS 9. In addition, the 2020 stress tests have been postponed and the implementation deadlines of Basel IV have been extended in different jurisdictions. Liquidity and capital relief are a temporary reversal of the increased prudential requirements that were imposed on banks in the aftermath of the 2007-2009 crisis. A question arises over whether the relaxation of the implementation of IFRS 9 is appropriate, as it may change the accounting of expected losses in the middle of a crisis. The pre-Covid-19 analysis of the impact of the 2007-2009 crisis and post-2008 regulatory reforms can be used to ascertain the resilience of the banking industry to the Covid-19 shock. Even though those reforms have made the banking system more resilient, it is not clear that this is enough for a shock of the type we are facing at present.

The Covid-19 epidemic has led to an impressive acceleration of the digitalisation process in the banking industry. For example, the industry has started operating almost entirely remotely quickly - online banking, remote working, e-commerce and electronic payments are on the rise and these trends are here to stay, particularly if social (physical) distancing has to remain in place in the medium term. This massive and sudden increase in digitalisation channels entails a

significant increase in operational risk – cyber risk in particular – that will require banks to make appropriate adjustments to their risk management functions. The banks that can react quickly will be better able to use and exploit the benefits of more advanced technology relative to before the crisis, but they will face the threat of digitally able Fintech and BigTech competitors in some segments of the business. The rapid shift towards a more digital world as a result of the confinement policies in response to Covid-19 is a reminder that the speed of change may take the sector (and everyone) by surprise. This change may also speed up the adoption of different forms of digital currencies and may put the focus on the introduction of central bank digital currency.

Member states of the EU face a further obstacle in trying to help their economies and the financial intermediaries in the form of state aid and resolution regulations. To ease the former, the European Commission adopted in March 2020 a temporary framework to enable member states to support their economies with different types of state aid, such as direct grants or subsidised state guarantees on bank loans. However, help for financial intermediaries is restricted. According to the Bank Recovery and Resolution Directive (BRRD), only in “circumstances of very extraordinary systemic stress, authorities may also provide public support instead of imposing losses in full on private creditors. The measures would nonetheless only become available after the bank’s shareholders and creditors bear losses equivalent to 8% of the bank’s liabilities and would be subject to the applicable rules of State aid.”

This 8% bail-in is applicable as of January 2016 – that is, bail-in is required even under systemic stress, for example out of a macroeconomic shock as in the Covid-19 crisis. This represents an obstacle to the creation of a bad bank where legacy assets from the past crisis would be parked, alleviating the balance sheet of banks to face the current crisis.

Furthermore, the massive expansionary fiscal policies that are currently being adopted by many countries, while limiting the damage from the crisis and therefore indirectly helping the banking sector, will most likely lead to significant increases in debt-to-GDP ratios (by an average of 20% in 2020 alone). This may raise sovereign debt sustainability problems over the medium term, in particular in the euro area, when central banks retreat from their asset purchase programmes. The consequence is that the doom loop of sovereign debt risk and bank risk that afflicted the euro area in the previous crisis may resurface. This may particularly be so if the economies in Southern Europe suffer disproportionately from the crisis and the ECB reaches the limits to its sovereign debt purchases. The Covid-19 epidemic has led to an impressive acceleration of the digitalisation process in the banking industry. For example, the industry has started operating almost entirely

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The question arises as to what the impact on the various players in the banking sector will be. BigTech companies have all the ingredients to get ahead, in general, in the post-Covid world. They have the technology, customer base and brand recognition, as well as vast amounts of data and deep pockets. They also have the incentives to get into financial services, as discussed before. However, before Covid-19, BigTech did not need the funding and had the customer data, while banks wanted the data. Post Covid-19, banks might have the upper hand in funding, with their deposit funding and large balance sheets, while BigTech has a higher cost of capital. Furthermore, banks are now back at centre stage of the intermediary chain as lenders to the real economy. Banks will distribute direct support and credit (typically with partial public guarantees), or both, with the backup of the central bank. Banks may also enjoy a revitalisation of relationship lending as they keep lending to customers over the crisis, with soft information more valuable than hard information.

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